

STUDIES OF SOME PHYSICO-CHEMICAL FACTORS IN THE ELECTRODEPOSITION OF SILVER.

BY SHRIDEAR SARVOTTAM JOSEI AND S. PADMANABHAN.

Results are given for the optimum conditions for the production of a smooth and adherent deposit of silver in respect of the duration of electrolysis, the inter-electrode distance, the electrolyte concentration, temperature, current and the influence of addition agents such as gelatin, turpentine and carbon disulphide.

Detailed measurements are made of the cathode efficiency of silver in the presence of methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and acetone whose proportions were varied over a wide range. Curves correlating the above two quantities show marked discontinuities indicative of complex formations in the conducting medium. Data are also given for the conductivity, refractive index and density, (and for methyl alcohol) transport number and viscosity.

A review of the literature shows that the data for the electrodeposition of silver are restricted principally to the use of the double cyanide of silver. The following experiments were carried out in order to investigate the utilisability of dilute silver nitrate solutions, in respect of the following factors :

1. The optimum conditions for the production of a smooth and adherent deposit of silver at various values of the duration of the electrolysis, the inter-electrode distance, the electrolyte concentration, temperature and current.
2. Cathode efficiency for the silver deposition in the presence of varying amounts of methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and acetone.
3. Presence in small quantities of such materials as gelatin, turpentine and carbon disulphide.

It also became necessary for the interpretation of the results obtained to determine the specific conductivity, refractive index and density of the bath solutions under conditions described later.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The circuit consisted of an adjustable resistance, an accurate milliammeter and an electrolytic bath screened from light kept at constant temperature. Two lead accumulator cells of a large capacity were used as the source of the current. The electrodes used were rectangular pieces of pure

silver of the size, $1.5'' \times 1'' \times 0.05''$; they were suspended parallel from an ebonite piece, the distance being varied as required.

The electrodes were first cleaned with emery paper and then with dilute alkali to remove traces of grease. They were then dipped in a very dilute solution of nitric acid and rinsed with distilled water. A thin coating of silver was given to the cathode by passing a current of about 60 to 70 milliamperes for about half an hour in a cyanide bath. After cleaning as before, the cathode was washed finally with an alcohol-ether solution and dried over the fan.

The stock solution consisted of $N/5$ -silver nitrate; it was prepared under red light and stored in red coloured bottles to minimise any light action. This was diluted to the required concentration in any given experiment. The precaution as to light action was also observed during electrolysis of the silver nitrate solutions used in this work. The following factors were studied in detail to investigate the optimum conditions under which a good adherent deposit of silver could be obtained, over ranges as indicated:

- (a) Current, 4 to 50 milliamps.
- (b) Concentration of electrolyte, $N/200$ to $N/20$.
- (c) Inter-electrode distance, 0.5 to 5 cm.
- (d) Temperature, 25° to 40° .
- (e) Time, 30 to 120 minutes.

These experiments showed that the following factors represented the optimum conditions: (a) 7 milliamps., (b) $N/20$ - AgNO_3 , (c) 0.5 cm., (d) 26° . (e) 38 mins. Under these *optimum conditions* measurements were made of the cathode efficiency for the silver deposition, in the presence of (i) methyl and ethyl alcohol and acetone, their proportions in all the cases being 15, 25, 35, 40, 50, 60 and 75 % by volume of the bath solution, and (ii) agents introduced in traces, *viz.*, carbon disulphide, gelatin and turpentine. The nature of the silver deposit produced in each of these experiments is also recorded, as examined with a microscope.

The current and the duration of electrolysis were kept constant at 7 milliamp. and 30 minutes in all the experiments made for the determinations of the cathode efficiency. The weight of silver deposit as calculated from Faraday's law for the above time is 0.01408 g. The cathode efficiency in experiment was given by the quantity, weight of the cathodic deposit of Ag $\times 100/0.01408$. These results are reported in Table I, (a—e).

To obtain further information in regard to the results obtained for the influence of methyl and ethyl alcohol and acetone on the depositional

behaviour of the bath solution, the corresponding electrolytic conductivity was determined on a Kohlrausch bridge with the usual precautions. The cell constant determined by using $N/50$ -KCl was found to be 0.3777 . These results are given in 4th and 5th columns of Tables II to IV

The refractive index for the sodium line was determined for each of the above mixtures by means of Pulfrich refractometer at $26^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$, with the usual precautions. The densities corresponding to these were determined at the above temperature. These results are given in Tables II to IV. In solutions containing methyl alcohol, measurements were made by Rao and Ramdas for the transport numbers and the corresponding viscosities. These have been shown graphically in Fig 3. Similarly the other quantities *viz.*, the cathode efficiency, refractive index, density and specific conductivity are plotted against percentages of the non-electrolyte added by appropriate selection of scale units in the same figure to economise space, in Figs. 1 to 3.

TABLE I.

(a) Variation of current.

Conc. = $N/20$ - $AgNO_3$. Temp. = 26° . Inter-electrode distance = 0.5 cm.
Time = 30 mins.

Current.	Nature of deposit.
50 m.amp.	'Tree' formation sets in as soon as electrolysis is started ; needle-shaped deposit.
40	'Tree' formation, slower ; size of needle-shaped crystals decreased.
30	'Tree' formation insensible ; deposit changes from needle-shaped crystals to big particles.
20	Particles decrease in size ; adherence partial.
10	Deposit irregular ; adherence better.
7	Deposit smooth, crystalline and adherent.
5	Deposit deteriorates.

(b) Variation of concentration of electrolyte.

Current = 7 m.amps. Time, inter-electrode distance and Temp. = 26°

Conc. of $AgNO_3$.	Nature of deposit.	Cathode efficiency.
$N/20$	Regular, adherent and smooth.	99.45
$N/100$	Less regular.	99.74
$N/200$	Black spongy needle-shaped crystals ; cathode turned dark.	

TABLE I (contd.).

(c) Variation of inter-electrode distance.

Conc. = $N/20$ - $AgNO_3$. Temp. = 26° . Current = 7 m. amps. Time = 30 min.

Inter-electrode distance.	Nature of deposit.
5 cm.	Coarse, irregular and adherent.
4	More regular but coarse.
3	More regular and smooth.
2	More smooth than before.
0.5	Smooth regular deposit of good adherence.

(d) Variation of temperature.

Current = 7 m. amp. Time = 30 mins. Inter-electrode distance = 0.5 cm.
Conc. = $N/20$ - $AgNO_3$.

Temp.	Nature of deposit.	Cathode efficiency.
25°	Regular, adherent and smooth.	99.89
27°	No appreciable change.	99.45
40°	Do.	99.65

(e) Variation of time.

Current = 7 m. amps. Temp. = 26° . Inter-electrode distance = 0.5 cm.
Conc. = $N/20$ - $AgNO_3$.

Time.	Nature of deposit.	Cathode efficiency.
30 min.	Regular, adherent and smooth.	99.45
60	Do	99.74
90	Deposit partially adherent; size of crystals increased.	
120	Adherence poor.	

TABLE II.

Electrolyte = $N/20$ - $AgNO_3$ soln. Non-electrolyte = Acetone. Temp. = $16 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

% Acetone in $N/20$ - $AgNO_3$ soln.	Cathode efficiency.		Sp. Conducty.		Refractive index.		Density.	
	Wt. of deposit.	Cathode efficiency.	Resistance (ohms).	Sp. conductivity (mhos).	Angle of prism.	Refractive index.	Wt. of soln.	Density.
0	0.0140 g.	99.5	246.6	0.00153	67°21'	1.332434	9.9926 g.	0.9979
15	0.0140	99.5	299.5	0.00126	66°1'	1.338761	9.8350	0.9822
25	0.0131	93.1	337.7	0.00112	64°46'	1.344906	9.7142	0.9701
35	0.01235	88.1	361.6	0.00104	63°57'	1.349056	9.5940	0.9581
40	0.0120	85.3	403.3	0.00094	63°27'	1.351619	9.5146	0.9502
50	0.0128	90.9	435.2	0.00087	62°41'	1.355604	9.3330	0.9320
60	0.01325	94.5	484.	0.00077	62°91'	1.35842	9.1350	0.9122
75	0.0137	97.3	474	0.00080	61°11'	1.363601	8.7824	0.8770

TABLE III.

Electrolyte = $N/20$ - $AgNO_3$. Non-electrolyte = EtOH. Temp. = $26 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

% EtOH in $N/20$ - $AgNO_3$ soln.	Cathode efficiency.		Sp. Conducty.		Refractive index.		Density.	
	Wt. of deposit.	Cathode efficiency.	Resistance (ohms).	Sp. conductivity (mhos).	Angle of prism.	Refractive index.	Wt. of soln.	Density.
0	0.0140 g.	99.5	246.6	0.00153	67°21'	1.332434	9.9926 g.	0.9979
15	0.0140	99.5	351.3	0.00107	65°54'	1.339327	9.8224	0.9809
25	0.0136	96.6	434	0.00087	64°34'	1.345929	9.6902	0.9677
35	0.0132	93.8	498	0.00076	63°40'	1.350501	9.5744	0.9561
40	0.0122	86.7	532	0.00071	63°10'	1.353081	9.4904	0.9477
50	0.0136	96.6	615	0.00061	62°23'	1.357127	9.2720	0.9260
60	0.0140	99.5	684.5	0.00055	61°49'	1.3602	9.0274	0.9016
75	0.0140	99.5	785.5	0.00080	61°25'	1.362246	8.6724	0.8662

TABLE IV.

 Electrolyte = $N/20$ - $AgNO_3$. Non-electrolyte = MeOH. Temp. = $26 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

	Cathode efficiency.		Sp. Conductivity.			Density	
	% of MeOH in $N/20$ f. $AgNO_3$ soln.	Time = 30 min. Current = 7 m. amp. Inter-electrode Dist. = 5 mm.	Resistance (ohms).	Conductivity (mhos).	Angle of prism.	Refract. index.	Wt. of an equal volume of water as soln. at the same temp. = 0.9988 Density of water at $26^\circ = 0.9968$.
	Wt of deposit.	Cathode efficiency.	Resistance (ohms).	Conductivity (mhos).	Angle of prism.	Refract. index	Wt of soln. Density
0	0.0140g	99.5	246.6	0.00153	$67^\circ 21'$	1.332434	0.9926
15	0.0126	89.5	321.4	0.00117	$66^\circ 45'$	1.335256	0.9794
25	0.0135	95.9	372	0.00101	$66^\circ 19'$	1.337321	0.9662
35	0.0140	99.5	432.3	0.00087	$65^\circ 58'$	1.339003	0.9520
40	0.0140	99.5	474.4	0.00080	$65^\circ 49'$	1.339732	0.9450
50	0.0136	96.6	536.6	0.00070	$65^\circ 37'$	1.340707	0.9282
60	0.01305	92.3	526.3	0.00072	$65^\circ 39'$	1.340543	0.9758
75	0.0122	86.7	457.6	0.00082	$66^\circ 4'$	1.338521	0.8762

TABLE V.

 Electrolyte = $N/20$ - $AgNO_3$. Current = 7 m. amp. Inter-electrode distance = 0.5 cm. Time = 30 min. Temp. = 26° .

% addition Agent.	Carbon disulphide.		Turpentine.		Gelatin.	
	Wt. of deposit.	Cathode efficiency.	Wt. of deposit.	Cathode efficiency.	Wt. of deposit.	Cathode efficiency.
0	0.0140 g.	99.5	0.0140 g.	99.5	0.0140 g.	99.5
1	0.0116	82.4	0.0108	76.7	0.0135	95.9
2	—	—	0.0086	61.1	0.0126	89.5
3	0.0090	63.9	0.0045	32.0	0.0122	86.7
5	0.0086	61.1	Black, needle shaped crystals; non-adherent deposit.	—	0.0111	82.4
10	Cathode darkened. Deposit non-adherent.		—	—	—	—

DISCUSSION.

The foregoing results show that the nature and the magnitude of an electrodeposit is conditioned by a wide variety of factors. These are discussed conveniently in respect of what has been designated as the cathode efficiency for the relevant ion, *viz.*, silver, which is 100% under ideal conditions. Any diminution in this appears to be due to such accessory circumstances as an incomplete adherence of deposit, occurrence of side reactions, *i.e.*, other than the main one for which the cathode efficiency is calculated. The discrepancy might also originate from solvational effects leading partly to the formation of molecular and ionic complexes in conducting mixtures. A number of experiments were carried out to investigate the influence of the factors designated *a*, *b*, *c*, *d*, and *e* (*vide*, p. 177) with a view to ascertain the optimum conditions for the relevant deposition and also in regard to the influence of (*f*) addition agents in small quantities and (*g*) proportion of a non-electrolyte varied over a wide range.

The process of electrodeposition is essentially a process of crystallisation. There are two stages in this process, *viz.*, (1) the formation of nuclei on the electrode surface and (2) growth of these crystal nuclei. Each of these has a different velocity. If the velocity of (1) is greater than that of (2), we get usually a fine deposit; whereas if the growth of crystal formation is more rapid, the deposit is coarser, and the big crystals are formed. The relation between the velocity of nuclei formation and the velocity of growth of crystals depends, besides the factors mentioned above *i.e.* (*a*) to (*g*), upon (*h*) nature of solvent, (*i*) nature of the metal deposited and (*j*) its valency.

Being of the 'nonpolarisable' type, it is to be anticipated from general considerations that the deposit of silver obtained from a solution of silver nitrate will be in the form of projecting needles except under special conditions. The smooth surface obtained from the double cyanide of silver and potassium is attributed to the formation of complex ions.

A study of the results in Table I *b* shows that very dilute solutions of silver nitrate are not suitable for the electrodeposition of silver. For example, at the concentration $N/200$, the cathode is completely darkened as soon as the current is passed. This is in conformity with the results of the previous workers. Kohlschutter and Toropoff (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1923, 19, 161) as a result of their investigations on the formation of silver black have emphasised that when a *very dilute* solution of silver nitrate is used, a black deposit is produced; it is due to the relative lack of crystal centres; under these conditions each discharged ion finds itself more or less isolated; consequently, it deposits itself as such and is not attached to a crystal centre, with the formation of grey crystalline silver. The sudden change to

grey silver on breaking the current is explained as an electro-surface tension phenomenon. The silver black with very large surface takes up the form of smallest surface on stopping the current, but when the current is flowing it is negatively polarised and the electrostatic repulsion of the charged particles overcomes the tendency to a surface diminution. Braun (*Ann. phys. chim.*, 1891, 42, 450) has shown that silver is only deposited when the intensity of the current has a certain maximum value which depends upon the strength of the solution. Gray (*Phil. Mag.*, 1887, 22, 389) has observed the marked value of a thorough cleaning of the electrodes and has given the size of cathode as ranging between 200 to 300 sq. cm./amp. current. He further adds that when the current is too small the deposited metal is not adherent and tends to grow out in crystals especially from any sharp edge or corner. An anode plate slightly larger than the cathode is recommended. Regarding the anode he is of opinion that it should have at least a surface of 400 sq. cm./ampere; very small anode plates become dark and spongy and gases are evolved from the surface, but when the plates are large they remain bright. Gray (*loc. cit.*) recommends a 5% (10% at the most) solution of silver nitrate; a silver anode, when not perfectly cleaned, is not completely dissolved; the outer layer of the metal remains as a loose skin. Barham and Taft (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 929) found that the deposits of silver obtained from silver nitrate in neutral, basic and acidic solutions were not good, were the poorest from neutral solutions, slightly better from basic and still better from acidic solutions. The deposits from neutral solutions were all badly burnt and in only a few cases, could be polished bright. Basic and acidic solutions also gave burnt deposits; they, however, in a number of cases took good polish. Barham and Taft (*loc. cit.*) from observations on variations of current density, found that above and below a certain critical value, the deposits distinctly deteriorate.

From results in Table Ie it is seen that too long a prolongation of electrolysis leans to a decrease in the adhesiveness of the deposit. For example, after 90 minutes, it was seen that loose particles of silver got detached from the cathode, and remained suspended near it. The above-mentioned effect might be ascribed in part to one or both of the following factors: (1) The crystal structure tends to be loose due to an excess of duration of electrolysis, especially in the case of dilute baths, due partly to the impoverishment in the corresponding content of dissolved silver. Evidence in respect of this is afforded by the general experience that fresh baths deteriorate on long standing and continued electrolysis. Our results on the reduction in cathode efficiency by use of very dilute bath solutions are in agreement with the above suggestion. (2) Nitric acid produced near the

anode would diffuse and exert a solvent action on the cathode; it is expected that this would be more pronounced with longer duration of the electrolysis.

Results in Table Id show that at higher temperatures, the cathode efficiency of silver is decreased. This agrees with the results of Leduc (*Compt. rend.*, 1902, 138, 237), who in the course of his investigations on the electrochemical equivalent of silver, found that nitric acid is not formed at the anode in appreciable quantities when normal solutions of silver nitrate are electrolysed at ordinary temperature. the anodic density being lower than 0.002 C.G.S. units. Under these conditions the cathodic deposit of silver is quite normal. If the anodic density is greater, the concentration lower or the temperature higher, nitric acid is formed and disturbs the deposition of silver at the cathode, which means a decrease in cathode efficiency, as suggested by our experiments in Table Id

Temperature affects the ionic velocity, degree of ionisation and the ionic mobility. In the case of copper sulphate a good deposit is obtained at higher temperature. This, however, does not hold good in the case of all metals as in the case of silver, where a decrease in cathode efficiency is noted (*cf.* Table I).

It is seen from results in Table Ia, that high current densities tend to form needle-shaped crystals when silver nitrate solutions are used for electrolysis. This is in agreement with the results of previous workers. Hughes and Wethrow (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 32, 1571) studied the effect of electrolytes on the electrodeposition of silver. In the case of nitric acid it was found that dense deposits could not be obtained if the E. M. F. was high, but with a low E. M. F. good crystalline deposits were produced. Samartzev (*Compt. rend. U. R. S. S.*, 1935, 2, 478) showed that metallic deposits on the active portions of cathode were possible only at definite current densities.

The ratio between the current density and the concentration of the metal ion at the immediate vicinity of the cathode determines the nature of deposit. It is easily seen that local E. M. F. develops on account of the fact that the electrode is different from what obtains in the bulk of the system, after the commencement of electrolysis. By increasing the current density the rate of nuclei-formation is increased; if this is out of phase with the contemporaneous process of crystallisation, the deposit would be loose and spongy. When the rate of nuclei-formation and crystal growth are balanced, a smooth deposit results.

It is seen from Table Ic that the quality of the deposit improves with the decrease in the inter-electrode distance. It has been shown already that

low current densities yield good deposits. A minimum of the foregoing quantities (7 m. amps and 0.5 cm.) represents the optimum conditions for silver deposition (*cf.* Table I a and c). Kremann (*Archiv Hemiju*, 1930, 4, 61) in the course of his study on the electrolysis of fused alloys produced by currents varied in the range 100-1000 amp./sq. cm. observed two determinants for the conductivity—one dependent on the fused state of the material and is presumably analogous to the so-called metallic conduction, and the other due to the electrolysis of the alloy, leading to changes in its composition in the vicinity of the electrodes, 'the metal of higher ionisation potential being deposited on the anode.' The latter effect becomes more marked as the current density increases and the distance between the electrodes is greater. These results suggest that a reduced inter-electrode distance would be the optimum condition corresponding to the use of low current densities. This deduction is in agreement with our results shown in Table Ic.

No precise information is, however, available in the literature for the correlation of the cathode efficiency with proportion of an addition agent in the electrolytic bath (*cf.* results in Table V). We have studied this in the case of turpentine, carbon disulphide and gelatine whose concentrations were varied over a wide range. The magnitude of the above influence is illustrated by the fact that 1% of turpentine, for example, reduces the cathode efficiency by 17.04%. With smaller proportions of the addition agents, well below 1% of the deposit, is adherent, smooth and bright with sensibly normal values for the cathode efficiency. The deposits corresponding to higher proportions of the addition agents possess but poor structures consisting of loosely formed big crystals and in some cases the cathode is completely darkened.

Various theories attempting to explain the influence of addition agents, which are generally organic or colloidal substances, exist in the literature. From conductivity and transport number measurements, Wulff and Ehrenberg (*Phot. Korrr.*, 1934, 70, 155; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1934, II, 3891) have shown that silver forms a complex ion with gelatin of the type $\{[Ag(Ge^-)_2]^- \}_n$. The apparently effective solubility of silver may be increased to about 100 times its normal value in water by the presence of gelatin. Frolich (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 67) found that gelatin has an 'isoelectric point' at p_n about 4.7 at which the material is electrolytically neutral and does not, therefore, migrate to either the anode or the cathode; at a p_n less than 4.7, *e.g.* in an acid copper solution, such colloids are positively charged and migrate towards the cathode surface and are actually included in the cathode deposits. Bancroft's view (*Trans.*

FIG. 1.

Temp. = $26 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

Amer. Electrochem. Soc., 1904, 6, 27; 1913, 23, 266) is that the crystal structure is decreased, when colloidal particles are thus adsorbed. It has been recently shown by Fuseya (*ibid.*, 1926, 50, 235; 1927, 52, 249) that substances such as citric and tartaric acids produce finer grained deposits of copper and silver from complex ions in the copper or silver solutions. It is possible that colloids may also form complex ions with the metals and be discharged on the cathode. Among the causes which normally promote the production of rough and 'treed' deposits is the presence of suspended impurities, especially conducting particles of carbon, metal, etc. derived from the anodes. Upthegrove and Baker (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1928, 53, 389) have observed that such impurities lodge themselves upon the cathode and serve as nuclei for the growth of large

grained crystals or 'trees'. Much of the effect of addition agents in reducing roughness is that of counteracting the influence of suspended matter. Kohlschutter and Sachacht (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1913, 19, 172) studied the influence of foreign substances on the deposition of silver. Silver was deposited electrolytically from a 0.05% solution of silver nitrate to which had been added just sufficient ammonium hydroxide to redissolve the precipitated silver oxide. This solution of 100 c.c. was electrolysed after the addition of one or two drops of sodium hydroxide. The solutions were electrolysed by a current of 3 m.amp. The silver was deposited in different forms in each case which was easily reproducible. It is shown that if the solutions were kept more than 15 to 20 hours quite different forms are obtained, so that in all the experiments freshly prepared silver nitrate was used. The action of the added substances in producing the different deposits is held to be due to the formation of colloidal metal hydroxides which are deposited on the cathode and form a type of filter, which conditions the distribution of the centres of crystallisation. Snowden (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1905, 9, 392) found that a good, coherent, crystalline deposit of silver from silver nitrate could be obtained by the rapid rotation of cathode and the separation of anodic and cathodic liquids. He is of the opinion that if means for a higher speed of rotation were available burnishing deposits would result. The addition of small quantities of glue had remarkable effects, smooth, bright, purple or yellow deposits with no visible crystalline structure being obtained which resemble some of Carry Lea's deposits from organic salts. Wernick (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, 24, 361) studied the effect of colloids on the electrodeposition of silver from silver nitrate solutions. He found that with the exception of dextrin there is a rough relationship between 'silver number' and the stiffness of deposit, the larger the 'silver number', the more closely grained was the deposit. Gorbunova (*Bull. Acad. Sci. U. R. S. S.*, 1933, 255) studied the structure of the electrolytic deposits of silver from its fused salts and found that they showed but feeble adherence and were readily removed by mere rubbing. Glazunov, Teindl and Halik (*Chem. Listy*, 1935, 29, 117, 131) studied the influence of small amounts of agar-agar and gelatin on the velocity of crystallisation of cathode deposits of silver from aqueous silver nitrate and found that the above velocity is reduced by the presence of even 0.03 to 0.15% of agar-agar or gelatin.

It is to be anticipated that the complex formation as disclosed by the above results would be simpler when the addition agents were of molecular weights smaller than these characteristic of colloids. Experiments were

FIG. 2.

Temp. = $26 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

therefore, carried out on measurements of the cathode efficiency in the presence of varying proportion of acetone (Fig. 1 and Table II), ethyl alcohol (Fig. 2 and Table III), and methyl alcohol (Fig. 3 and Table IV). It is seen from these results that the above quantity is affected considerably due to the presence of the substances mentioned above. For example, in the case of acetone the cathode efficiency is almost constant at 99.45% in the range 0 to 15% of acetone; it decreases very rapidly to a minimum at 40% and then increases continuously up to 75%. The influence of ethyl and methyl alcohol in respect of the above quantity (Fig. 2 and 3) is substantially analogous. It is extremely likely that these marked changes of gradient on the cathode efficiency—non-electrolyte concentration curves in Figs. 1-3 are due to some interaction between the medium and

the conducting material. A number of further properties such as the conductivity, the refractive index and density for the same mixtures were, therefore, studied. Schalls (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1894, 15, 701) found that very usually, the conductivity is decreased when the water of solution is replaced in part by alcohol, which is in agreement with the foregoing results. Hantzsch (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1900, 26, 332) studied the influence of non-electrolytes on the conductivity of electrolytes. The addition of methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and acetone to aqueous solutions of the alkali or alkaline earth metal diminished the conductivity slightly and approximately to the same extent. He also found that conductivity of ammoniacal solutions of calcium chloride is appreciably less than the sum of the conductivities considered separately. The difference is greater in the case of ammoniacal silver nitrate. The latter contains the complex ion $\text{Ag}(\text{NH}_3)_2$, so that the mobility of this ion might be about the same as that of the simple ion Ag. The results are here interpreted by Werner's theory. Jones and Rouiller (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 28, 427), while studying this relative migration velocity of the ions of silver nitrate in water, methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol and acetone, have studied the conductivity of such solutions. The conductivity was determined at 0° and 25°, all the measurements being made with 0.02*N* solutions. Observations confirmed that the velocity of the slower ion increases with the rise of temperature. This is not so in solutions in pure methyl alcohol or in a solution of methyl alcohol and water containing 75% of the former or in a mixture of methyl alcohol and acetone. The relative migration velocities are influenced largely by the nature of the solvent and this is probably due to the varying degrees of combination of the solvent with one of these ions.

The specific conductivity and refractive index graphs (Fig. 3) show a remarkable similarity, *i. e.*, while the specific conductivity decreases, refractive index increases gradually almost to the same extent until in the former case a minimum and in the later case a maximum are obtained. The corresponding curves in Figs. 2 and 3 show essentially the same feature. The occurrence of this discontinuity can, therefore, be taken as indicative of some complex formation. It is necessary to point out at this stage that although maxima and minima occur in all the curves showing the variation of the foregoing properties with the proportion of the non-electrolyte (except in the case of density where the discontinuity is markedly flatter) the actual position is not unique for all the curves. This would appear to be in accord with general experience of inflections on curves relating physical properties with chemical composition in various systems.

FIG. 3.

Temp. = $26 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

ELECTROCHEMISTRY SECTION,
 CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
 BENARES HINDU UNIVERSITY, BENARES.

Received February 23, 1938.